

FIZIKA FANIDAN LABORATORIYA MASHG'ULOTLARIGA STEAM TEXNOLOGIYASINI INTEGRATSIYALASHNING DOLZARBLIGI VA AFZALLIKLARI

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Kalit so'zlar: maktab, STEAM, texnologiya, nazariya, jihoz

Dolzarbligi: Maktabda fizika laboratoriya jihozlarning kamligi, narxi qimmatligi va hamma maktablarda yo'qligi

Vazifasi: Fizika laboratoriya jihozlari kam bo'lsa ham o'quvchilarning o'zlari uy sharoitida yasashlari mumkin albatta xafvsizlik qoidalari amal qilgan holda STEAM texnologiyasini qo'llash orqali

Afzalligi: O'quvchilar fizika fanida faqat nazariya bilan cheklanib qolmaydilar balki o'zlari ham yasab ko'rib tezroq o'rganadilar va hayotga tadbiiq qilib ko'radilar va tezroq o'rganishadi.

Kaloriometr bu fizikada issiqlik miqdorini topish uchun kerak bo'ladigan fizik jihoz hisoblanadi.

1. Tashqi qobiq u aluminiydan yasalgan
2. Ichida ham xuddi tashqi qobiqdagiday aluminiy idish bor
3. Ichki va tashqi idishlar orasida issiqlik yoki sovuq o'tkazmaydigan modda bor. Po'kak ham bo'laveradi chunki po'kak ham issiqni ham sovuqni ham chiqarmaydi ham o'tkazmaydi ham.
4. Termometr aralashtirgich
5. Suvni isitadigan isitish moslamasi

isitgich moslamasi

aralashtirgich

Kaliorometr idishlari

Kaliorometrni narxi o'zi 260 ming so'm ekan. Yetkazib berish xizmati bilan 300 ming so'mga tushadi. O'zimiz uy sharoitida shu kaloorometrni yasasak maksimal narxi 50-60 ming atrofida bo'ladi.

Kaliorometrni yasash uchun 2 ta idish va po'kak va termometr aralashtirgich va isitish moslamasi kerak.

Kaliorometrni yana uy sharoitida taxlashni afzalligi o'quvchilar tushunishlari oson va tez o'rganib olishadi. Zarur bo'lgan vaqti o'zlari bimalol taxlab olib ishlatishadi.

• Jismlarni zaryadpanganligini sezadigan aparatga elektroskop deyiladi. elektroskop quyidagi qismlardan iborat.

1. Metall korpus;
2. Shisha devorlar;
3. Metall tayoq;
4. Metall barglari(barglari);
5. Plastik vilka.

Elektroskop (elektr... va ... skopiya) — elektr zaryadlarni sezadigan va ularning kattaliklarini taxminan aniqlaydigan oddiy asbob. E. bir uchiga 2 ta metall yaproqcha sharcha

mahkamlangan sterjendan iborat. Sterjen shisha idish ichiga joylashtirilib, izolyatsiyalovchi materialdan tayyorlangan tiqin yordamida mahkamlangan. Sharchaga zaryadlangan jism tekkanda zaryadning bir qismi yaproqchalarga o'tib, ular birbiridan itariladi; yaproqchalarning ochilish burchagi elektr zaryadi miqdoriga mutanosib bo'ladi. Yaproqchalarning ochilish burchagiga qarab jismning zaryadi haqida fikr yuritish mumkin.

- Elektroskop narxiga kelsak buni narxini topa olmadim bu jihoz ham kaliorometr narxiga yaqin turadi. Uy sharoitida yasashda maksimal ketadigan xarajat 50 ming ga yaqin bo'ladi.
- Elektroskopni uy sharoitida tayyorlash uchun bizga shisha idish metall sterjen va falga qog'ozlari va idish og'zini berkitadigan propka va metall sharcha kerak bo'ladi
- O'quvchilar o'zlari bemalol yasab olsalar bo'laveradi. Eng muhimi xafvsiz hisoblanadi yasashda. Shu bahonada o'quvchilar qiziqib tez o'rganishadi mavzuni ham laboratoriya ishini ham

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